

A Study on Risk Involved in the Online Shopping

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Introduction :

Today, people are living in the digital environment. Earlier, internet was used as the source for information sharing, but now life is somewhat impossible without it. Everything is linked with the World Wide Web, whether it is business, social interaction or shopping. Moreover, the changed lifestyle of individuals has changed their way of doing things from traditional to the digital way in which shopping is also being shifted to online shopping.

Online shopping is the process of purchasing goods directly from a seller without any intermediary, or it can be referred to as the activity of buying and selling goods over the internet. Online shopping deals provide the customer with a variety of products and services, wherein customers can compare them with deals of other intermediaries also and choose one of the best deals for them.

Risk Involved in Online Shopping :

Financial Risk :

Risk creates valuable part in the decision of online purchasing. The main point is about insecurity which leads the high negative perspective in web purchasing. The decision of online shopping comprises many risks. The risk creates many problems only when the result of online shopping is not sure. Financial risk occurs at very first stage of online shopping after order placing. Before purchasing and post purchasing also includes the prescribed risks.

Product Risks :

The products risk also called the performance risk. The performance risks can be defined as, the chances of the failure of products to meet its user's requirements. This is only the way why consumers do not shop online. Product risks include many categories of product failure among users. These categories include physically examination of a product as well as product attributes. This risk also includes the financial damage of a product as well as loss of goods from initial stage to final stage. The main reason to think is that it may be fraud activities which contain money loss.

Convenience Risks :

There is a much absence of trust in the judgment of online shopping. There are a number of pressures and threats which exist in the type of web based purchasing. These numbers of threats include many factors such as privacy policy or about identity etc. The main point which is positive or has a main strength about product is that time management concept is included in this type of shopping decision.

Non Delivery Risks :

There is also a loss of delivery of goods to wrong people at wrong place. The other factor is that a firm or organization does not meet their promise of time period. It delays. During the shipping process the products may be harmed. Its packing may not be proper as it should.

Return Policy Risks :

The simplest way to sale the goods electronically is just to assure about "Money Back Guarantee". It is the way which ensure consumers if they are not

satisfied with the product, they can back their products at any time without any hesitation. This method has positively or negatively impact on customer's choice.

No sales assistance Risk :

In a store, there's usually someone to help you but online, you're on your own. If you're confused or have questions, it's just too bad for you. You might have to make blind purchases and mistakes you'll regret later because there was no one to talk to.

No support for local retailers Risk :

If everyone started doing all their shopping online, all the local stores would go out of business. When all the stores in town are gone, we'll have to drive further and further away to shop at a real store.

Conclusion :

Today, many people now prefer to shop online over going into physical stores. The advent of the internet and improved logistics technology has made online shopping a cheap and convenient alternative. However, this convenience has its own cost. Increased pollution and waste, along with the destruction of small businesses, are all negative impacts of online shopping. In this article, it has made an attempt of all the pros and cons of online shopping.

References :

- Zeithaml, V.A., M.J. Bitner, et al. (2006) : "Services marketing: Integrating customer focus across the firm."
- Arnold, M.J., and Reynolds, K.E. : Hedonic shopping motivations, *Journal of retailing*, 79(2), pp. 77-95, 2003.